

1 **Pepsin treatment of whey proteins under high pressure produces hypoallergenic**
2 **hydrolysates**

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24 **ABSTRACT**

25 Previous results have shown that pepsin treatment under high hydrostatic pressure (400
26 MPa, 37°C, 30 min) produces a whey protein hydrolysate that exhibits reduced IgE
27 binding and improved functional properties [Chicón, et al. (2009) Food Hydrocolloids,
28 23, 593]. This work investigates the eliciting, sensitizing and immunogenic properties of
29 this hydrolysate (HWP). A BALB/c mouse model of cow's milk allergy was used for the
30 evaluation of the ability of HWP to induce anaphylactic reactions, antibody production
31 and cytokine responses in comparison with intact whey proteins (WP). HWP did not
32 contain intact allergens, including β -Lg, and 50% of its peptides had molecular masses
33 between 10 and 3 kDa. Challenge with HWP did not induce anaphylaxis signs, body
34 temperature changes or release of mouse mast cell proteinase-1 in BALB/c mice
35 sensitized to WP. Furthermore, immunization with HWP did not lead to the production
36 of WP-specific antibodies nor to allergic reactions upon HWP or WP challenge, and thus,
37 it can be considered hypoallergenic. However, HWP retained sufficiently
38 immunogenicity to stimulate Th2 responses in the spleen cells of WP or HWP sensitized
39 mice. These characteristics make HWP a good candidate to be used in the management
40 of milk allergy in diagnosed patients or to induce tolerance to milk whey proteins.

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42 **1 Introduction**

43 Cow's milk allergy is one of the most common types of food allergy during early
44 childhood. In infants diagnosed with cow's milk allergy or at high risk of allergy
45 development, the use of hypoallergenic formulas is frequently recommended (Muraro et
46 al., 2014; de Silva et al., 2014). Hypoallergenic formulas are based on hydrolysed cow's
47 milk proteins which show reduced allergenicity with declining peptide size. Accordingly,
48 they are classically categorized as extensively (<3 kDa) or partially (3-10 kDa)
49 hydrolysed, on the basis of the molecular weight distribution of their peptide fragments,
50 and designed, respectively, to avoid clinical symptoms or to prevent potential
51 sensitization (Bøgh et al., 2015). European guidelines on hypoallergenic and follow-on
52 formulas establish that their hypoallergenicity needs to be assessed by showing that they
53 are not able to sensitize animals to the protein source they derive from (Commission
54 Directive 96/4/EC). This has prompted the validation of animal models of cow's milk
55 allergy with the purpose to provide scientific data to support the hypoallergenicity of these
56 infant formulas (van Esch et al., 2013).

57 Hypoallergenic formulas are frequently manufactured from the milk whey protein
58 fraction, which contains a high amount of β -lactoglobulin (β -Lg) (about half of the protein
59 content of milk whey), a major allergen absent from human milk (Roth-Walter et al.,
60 2014). Susceptibility to proteolysis of β -Lg is relatively low and various chemical and
61 physical treatments have been used with the purpose to promote its hydrolysis, such as
62 the use of denaturing agents, heating or high pressure (López-Fandiño, 2005; Bu et al.,
63 2013; Cheison & Kulozik, 2015). Enzymatic treatments under high hydrostatic pressure
64 considerably enhance proteolysis of β -Lg and reduce its IgE-binding (Chicón et al., 2008
65 a and b; Peñas et al., 2006 a and b). The effect of pressure has been traced to protein

66 unfolding that exposes to the enzymatic action regions not easily accessible in the native
67 structure. Thus, proteolysis under high pressure, in contrast to atmospheric pressure, leads
68 to a rapid removal of the intact protein and to the accumulation of large and intermediate
69 size peptides, which are then further degraded to smaller fragments (Belloque et al.,
70 2007).

71 High pressure might, therefore, constitute an alternative to the exhaustive enzymatic
72 hydrolysis treatments used in the processing of hypoallergenic formulas, that release short
73 peptides and free amino acids adversely affecting their functional and organoleptic value
74 (Abd El-Salam & El-Shibiny, 2015; Liu et al., 2014). From the point of view of the
75 manufacturing industry, optimization of the proteolysis process is essential, not only to
76 eliminate the allergenic potential, but also to maintain or enhance the nutritional and
77 functional properties, such as palatability or emulsification, which are important for
78 preparing stable formulations.

79 Previous results have shown that pepsin treatment under high hydrostatic pressure
80 produces a whey protein hydrolysate that exhibits reduced IgE binding and improved heat
81 stability and emulsion activity. The combination of low antigenicity with the capacity to
82 form emulsions may allow the production of milk-based ingredients for hypoallergenic
83 preparations (Chicón et al., 2009). The aim of this work was to investigate the eliciting,
84 sensitizing and immunogenic properties of this hydrolysate. To this end, a BALB/c mouse
85 model of cow's milk allergy was used for the evaluation of the ability of the hydrolysate
86 to induce anaphylactic reactions, antibody production and cytokine responses in
87 comparison with intact whey proteins.

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90 **2 Materials and Methods**

91 **2.1 Proteins and mice**

92 Whey protein isolate (WP) (84.5 % protein content determined by Kjeldahl method) was
93 obtained from a national company. Porcine pepsin (EC 3.4.23.1, 3440 U/mg), α -
94 lactalbumin (α -La) and β -lactoglobulin (β -Lg) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St.
95 Louis, MO, USA). The lipopolysaccharide (LPS) levels of the proteins and pepsin were
96 quantified by the Pierce LAL Chromogenic Endotoxin Quantitation Kit (Thermo
97 Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and, after purification of α -La by size exclusion
98 chromatography (Pablos-Tanarro et al., 2016), all levels were <1 EU/mg.

99 Six-week-old female specific-pathogen-free BALB/c mice were purchased from Charles
100 River Laboratories (Saint Germain sur l'Arbresle, France), housed under standard
101 conditions and fed an animal protein-free diet (SAFE, Route de Saint Bris, France). All
102 protocols involving animals followed the European legislation (Directive 2010/63/UE)
103 and were approved by the CSIC Bioethics Committee and the Comunidad de Madrid (Ref
104 PROEX 089/15).

105 **2.2 Hydrolysis of whey proteins under high hydrostatic pressure**

106 WP, dissolved in MilliQ water (5 mg/mL) and adjusted to pH 1.5, was pre-incubated at
107 37°C for 10 min prior to the addition of 172 U/mg protein of porcine pepsin. The mixture
108 was immediately vacuum sealed in polyethylene bags, avoiding headspace, and
109 pressurized at 400 MPa and 37±2°C using an Iso-lab 900 High Pressure Food Processor
110 (Mod FPG7 100:9/2C, Stansted Fluid Power Ltd. Harlow, Essex, UK) with water as
111 pressure-transmitting fluid. The pressure was raised at a rate of 600 MPa/min, maintained
112 for 30 min, and released in less than 4 s. The conditions to produce WP hydrolysed with

113 pepsin under high pressure (HWP) were chosen in the basis of previous experiments,
114 which showed complete elimination of the intact allergenic proteins, reduced IgE-binding
115 and improved functional properties (Chicón et al., 2009). As a reference, hydrolysis was
116 also conducted at atmospheric pressure (0.1 MPa) at 37°C, under continuous shaking, for
117 up to 24 h. After removal from the high pressure unit or the water bath, pepsin reaction
118 was stopped by raising the pH to 7.0 with 2 N NaOH. Samples were lyophilized, their
119 protein content determined by the Kjeldahl method, and stored at -20 °C until used.

120 **2.3 MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry**

121 Peptide mass distribution of the hydrolysates was analyzed by MALDI-TOF using a
122 Bruker AUTOflex Speed spectrometer (Bruker Daltonik GmbH, Bremen, Germany). The
123 hydrolysates (0.5 µL dissolved at a concentration of 5 µg/mL) were loaded on a dry 2.5-
124 dihydroxybenzoic acid (DHB) matrix spot (0.5 µL of 20 mg/mL DHB in ACN/methanol,
125 70/30%, containing 1% TFA) onto a Bruker Anchorchip target. All mass spectra were
126 initially calibrated with Peptide Calibration Standard and Protein Calibration Standard I
127 (Bruker Daltonik). Mass spectra were acquired in positive reflection, by summing 50 laser
128 pulses at a fixed slide target position, using a 337 nm nitrogen laser and an acceleration
129 voltage of 20 kV.

130 **2.4 RP-HPLC-MS/MS**

131 For RP-HPLC analyses with UV detection (214 nm) and on-line electrospray ionization
132 (ESI-MS/MS), an Agilent 1100 Series HPLC (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn,
133 Germany) and an Esquire 3000 mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonik, Bremen, Germany)
134 were used. The hydrolysate (HWP) was analysed after a reducing step using
135 dithiothreitol, at a final concentration of 70 mM and pH 7.0, for 1 h at 37°C (Chicón et
136 al., 2008 b). Chromatographic separations were performed with a RP318 column (250 x

137 4.6 mm, Bio-Rad). The operating conditions were: flow rate, 0.8 mL/min; injection
138 volume, 50 µl; solvent A, 0.37 mL/L trifluoroacetic acid in Milli-Q water; and solvent B,
139 0.27 mL/L trifluoroacetic acid in HPLC grade acetonitrile. Elution was conducted with a
140 linear gradient of solvent B in A from 0 to 70% in 75 min, followed by 100% B for 30
141 min. Ion source parameters were: nebulizer pressure, 60 psi; dry gas, 12 L/min and dry
142 temperature, 350°C. Using Data Analyses TM (version 3.0; Bruker Daltonik), the m/z
143 spectral data were processed and transformed to spectra representing mass values.
144 Biotoools (version 2.1; Bruker Daltonik) was used to process the MS(n) spectra and
145 Mascot software (version 2.3.3, Matrix Science, London, UK) to perform peptide
146 sequencing. For each sample, a minimum Mascot score corresponding to $P < 0.05$ was
147 considered as a prerequisite for 149 validation of peptide identification.

148 **2.5 Sensitization and challenge of mice**

149 Mice were distributed in 2 groups (n=12) and sensitized by oral gavage, during three
150 consecutive days on the first week and once per week during the following 4 weeks, with
151 5 mg of protein per mouse of either intact WP or HWP in PBS plus 10 µg of cholera toxin
152 (CT) (List Biologicals, Campbell, USA). Control mice (n=6) just received 10 µg of CT
153 in PBS. One week after the last sensitization dose, half of the WP- and HWP-treated mice
154 were challenged with WP and the other half with HWP. Oral challenge (20 mg protein
155 per mouse) was followed by an intraperitoneal (i.p.) challenge (100 µg protein per mouse)
156 40 min apart. Control mice were only challenged with WP. Anaphylactic responses were
157 evaluated by scoring clinical signs and rectal temperature 30 min after each challenge, as
158 described in Pablos-Tanarro et al. (2016). Mice were then euthanized by CO₂ inhalation.

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161 **2.6 Detection of specific immunoglobulins and mouse mast cell protease-1**

162 Blood and faeces were collected after each sensitization dose and after i.p. challenge. Sera
163 were obtained by centrifugation at 2500 x g for 10 min and kept at -20°C until analysis,
164 and faeces were lyophilised. Serum levels of total, WP-specific, and HWP-specific IgE
165 and IgG1 were quantified by ELISA as previously described by Pablos-Tanarro et al.
166 (2016). Briefly, 96-well plates were coated with 0.5 µg/well of either WP or HWP for
167 measurement of specific-antibodies, or with 0.2 µg/well of rat anti-mouse IgE and IgG1
168 (BD Biosciences, San Diego, USA) for total IgE and IgG1 quantification and for building
169 reference curves. After an overnight incubation at 4°C, plates were blocked and incubated
170 with diluted serum samples (1:100 for total IgE, 1:30 for WP-specific IgE, 1:5 for HWP-
171 specific IgE, 1:10000 for total IgG1, 1:1000 for WP-specific IgG1 and 1:100 for HWP-
172 specific IgG1) or serial dilutions of mouse IgE and IgG1 isotypes (BD Biosciences).
173 Detection was carried out by adding biotinylated rat anti-mouse IgE and IgG1, followed
174 with an avidin-horseradish peroxidase incubation step (BD Biosciences). Reactions were
175 developed with ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzthiazoline-6-sulfonate) as substrate
176 (Roche, Mannheim, Germany) and read at 405 nm.

177 Detection of total, WP-specific and HWP-specific IgA was carried out in the supernatants
178 of lyophilized faecal samples homogenized in PBS during 3 h and centrifuged at 4000 x
179 g for 10 min. Quantification of IgA levels was performed as described for IgE and IgG1,
180 with the exception of using **rat** anti-mouse IgA antibodies and mouse IgA isotype control
181 for the reference curves (BD Biosciences). Supernatants were diluted 1:100 for total IgA,
182 1:30 for WP-specific IgA and 1:5 for HWP-specific IgA.

183 Mast cell degranulation was evaluated in serum samples collected after i.p. challenge by
184 determining the concentration of mouse mast cell protease-1 (*mMCP-1*) using a
185 commercial ELISA kit (eBioscience, San Diego, USA).

186 **2.7 Passive cutaneous anaphylaxis assay**

187 Passive cutaneous anaphylaxis (PCA) assays were performed as described in López-
188 Expósito et al. (2012). Naïve BALB/c mice (2 per PCA test) were injected intradermally
189 in the right ear pinna with 20 μ L of either unheated or heat-inactivated (56°C for 3 hours;
190 Li et al., 2000) pooled sera (n=6) from WP- or HWP-sensitized mice, and with pooled
191 sera from control mice (n=6) in the left ear pinna. Twenty four hours later, mice were
192 injected intravenously with 200 μ g of the respective protein, either WP or HWP, in 100
193 μ L of 1% Evans blue dye (Sigma-Aldrich). One hour after protein inoculation, mice were
194 euthanized and ears were individually collected and incubated overnight in N,N-
195 dimethylformamide (Sigma-Aldrich). The absorbance of the supernatant was measured
196 at 655 nm, in order to quantify the extravasation of the dye by extrapolation from a
197 reference curve with known amounts of Evans blue, and normalized to the weight of each
198 ear.

199 **2.8 Splenocyte culture, cell proliferation and cytokine quantitation**

200 Spleens were individually collected and processed under sterile conditions. Splenocytes
201 were cultured in 48-well plates (4×10^6 cells/mL) and stimulated, in duplicate, with
202 concanavalin A (2.5 μ g/mL), as positive control, RPMI-1640 medium, as negative
203 control, WP, HWP, α -La or β -Lg (200 μ g/mL). CFSE-based proliferation assays were
204 carried out as previously described by Lozano-Ojalvo et al. (2016). After 72 hours of
205 incubation at 37 °C in 5% CO₂, cells were harvested for analytical flow cytometry with a
206 Gallios instrument (Beckman Coulter, Krefeld, Germany) and supernatants were

207 collected and stored at -80 °C until analysis of cytokines (IL-5, IL-13, TNF- α and IFN-
208 γ) by ELISA, using commercial kits (eBioscience).

209 **2.9 Statistical analyses**

210 Data are presented as means \pm SEM, excluding clinical signs, which are expressed as
211 medians. Differences were determined by applying one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey
212 post-hoc test, except for the clinical sign scores, which were evaluated by Mann-Whitney
213 U test. P values $<$ 0.05 were considered statistically significant. Statistical analyses were
214 performed using GraphPad Prism v5 (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, USA).

215 **3 Results**

216 **3.1 Characterization of the whey protein hydrolysate obtained under high pressure**

217 The extent of hydrolysis of WP with pepsin under high pressure was evaluated by RP-
218 HPLC. High pressure promoted a very rapid disappearance of both α -La and β -Lg,
219 leaving no traces of intact proteins after 30 min of treatment with pepsin at 400 MPa. In
220 contrast, β -Lg resisted pepsin digestion at atmospheric pressure and did not disappear
221 until 24 hours of hydrolysis (Figure 1).

222 The peptide mass distribution of HWP was compared with that of the hydrolysate
223 produced at atmospheric pressure under conditions leading to the complete removal of
224 the main whey proteins (24 hours). Molecular masses, as estimated by MALDI-TOF MS,
225 were lower than 10 kDa in both cases (Figure 2). However, almost 50% of the peptides
226 contained in HWP had molecular masses above of 3 kDa, whereas hydrolysis at
227 atmospheric pressure led to smaller fragments, with approximately 90% below 3 kDa,
228 which matches the presence of more early-eluting peaks in the RP-HPLC chromatogram
229 of the later (Figure 1).

230 RP-HPLC-MS/MS was used to label the peptides with molecular mass lower than 3 kDa
231 in HWP. Eighty fragments corresponding to β -Lg and 22 corresponding to α -La were
232 identified (supplementary Table S1). Peptides from β -Lg covered most of its sequence,
233 with several of them included in regions of the protein previously identified as major IgE-
234 binding epitopes, such as β -Lg (43-62), β -Lg (86-100) and β -Lg (127-147) (Sélo et al.,
235 1999, Järvinen et al., 2001; Cerecedo et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2010, Benedé et al., 2014).
236 On the other hand, it is likely that peptides, such as those including Cys₆₆ [β -Lg (58-74)
237 and β -Lg (59-73)] are linked to those containing Cys₁₆₀ [β -Lg (156-162)] through a
238 disulphide bond. Fragments from α -La related to the IgE-binding epitopes α -La (1-26)
239 and α -La (93-102) were also found, although no peptides corresponding to the area
240 between amino acids 50 and 83, which comprises the epitope α -La (47-58) (Järvinen et
241 al., 2001), were identified.

242 **3.2 Eliciting capacity**

243 Clinical signs and body temperature were evaluated after oral and i.p. challenges with
244 WP and HWP in mice administered WP or HWP plus CT, and compared with control
245 mice challenged only with WP. No anaphylaxis was observed after oral challenge with
246 either WP or HWP in any experimental group (data not shown). However, 30 min after
247 i.p. challenge, mice sensitised to WP showed severe anaphylactic signs and a pronounced
248 temperature drop when challenged with WP, while only one out of six mice from the
249 HWP group showed very mild symptoms (score 1) (Figure 3 a and b). No anaphylactic
250 reactions were observed after i.p challenge with HWP in any of the groups. In agreement
251 with these results, elevated serum levels of *mMCP-1*, denoting activation and
252 degranulation of mast cell levels, were only significantly elevated in WP-sensitised mice
253 challenged with WP (Figure 3 c).

254 **3.3 Sensitizing capacity: antibody responses**

255 Total and antigen-specific antibody responses were monitored weekly throughout the
256 sensitization period (Figure 4). Total IgE increased in the WP and HWP groups up to the
257 4th week, with no significant differences between them. The highest levels of IgG1 were
258 reached on the 5th week and corresponded to the WP group. While, the concentrations of
259 total IgE and IgG1 were higher in the WP and HWP groups than in the control group by
260 end of the experimental period, no significant differences were found among the 3 groups
261 in total faecal IgA (Figure 4 a, c and e).

262 Sensitization with WP induced significant levels of serum WP-specific IgE and IgG1 and
263 faecal WP-specific IgA. However, HWP failed to generate WP-specific antibody
264 responses (Figure 4 b, d and f). Furthermore, no HWP-specific IgE or IgA antibodies
265 could be detected in any group (not shown), although HWP-specific IgG1 was present in
266 both, WP and HWP sera, with a significantly higher level in the HWP group (Figure 4 g).

267 In order to estimate the functionality of the specific IgE and IgG1 antibodies generated in
268 each group, PCA assays were performed. Inoculation of sera from the WP group, but not
269 of that from the control group, induced positive reactions following the intravenous
270 administration of WP. In addition, when the pooled sera were heated at 56°C during 3 h
271 to inactivate IgE, dye extravasation significantly decreased (Figure 5). Passive
272 immunization of mice with sera from the HWP group, devoid of detectable specific-IgE,
273 caused a lower, but significant, dye extravasation following HWP injection which, as
274 expected, was not modified upon heating. These results suggested the generation, in mice
275 from the HWP group, of biologically active HWP-specific IgG1, able to mediate allergic
276 reactions.

277 **3.4 Immunogenic capacity: cellular responses**

278 Spleen cells were cultured and stimulated with WP and HWP, and T cell proliferative
279 responses and Th1/Th2 cytokine production were evaluated. Concanavalin A, a mitogen
280 able to stimulate T lymphocytes used as positive control, induced a vigorous cell
281 proliferation in all groups (Table 1). Spleen cells from WP- and HWP-administered mice
282 exhibited significant proliferative responses to both WP and HWP, as compared with non-
283 stimulated cells (RPMI), with no differences in the outcomes of WP or HWP stimulation
284 within each group or between both groups.

285 As expected, splenocytes from mice from the WP group produced allergy-associated Th2
286 cytokines (IL-13 and IL-5) following stimulation with WP. Incubation with HWP induced
287 a lower, albeit significant, response (Figure 6 a and c). Spleen cells from mice from the
288 HWP group released comparably less IL-13 and IL-5 upon WP stimulation and similar
289 levels upon HWP stimulation. With respect to Th1 cytokines, spleen cells from WP and
290 HWP groups produced similar levels of IFN- γ and TNF- α as a result of incubation with
291 WP, while HWP did not induce the release of these cytokines in any of these groups
292 (Figure 6 b and d).

293 Splenocyte incubation with the major whey proteins, α -La and β -Lg, revealed that β -Lg
294 induced the strongest cytokine responses; in most cases, equivalent to those induced by
295 WP, whereas α -La did not significantly increase cytokine production (Figure 6).

296 **4 Discussion**

297 Treatment with pepsin under high hydrostatic pressure (400 MPa) produced in 30 min a
298 whey protein hydrolysate devoid of intact allergens, including β -Lg, a protein very
299 resistant to proteolysis at acidic pH (Figure 1). Approximately, 50% of the fragments
300 contained in HWP had molecular masses above of 3 kDa, while conditions that led to the
301 complete hydrolysis of β -Lg at atmospheric pressure yielded most fragments (90%)

302 below 3 kDa (Figure 2). Hydrolysis of β -Lg with pepsin under high pressure follows a
303 progressive proteolysis mechanism that involves a very rapid disappearance of the protein
304 into large fragments, which are then degraded into smaller peptides. In contrast, at
305 atmospheric pressure, the persistence of the intact protein and the comparatively much
306 lower amount of medium-size fragments indicate that proteolysis is more difficult, but
307 once intermediate peptides are released, there are no restrictions on their hydrolysis to
308 smaller fragments (Belloque et al., 2007, Chicón et al., 2008b).

309 Previous work showed that the large, and presumably hydrophobic, fragments contained
310 in HWP contributed to enhance the heat stability and maintain the capacity to efficiently
311 form emulsions of the original WP, while they retain a reduced, but noticeable, residual
312 binding to IgE from egg allergic patients (Chicón et al., 2009). In fact, RP-HPLC-MS/MS
313 revealed the presence of allergenic epitopes from both β -Lg and α -La (supplementary
314 table S1). Challenge with HWP, however, did not induce anaphylaxis signs, body
315 temperature changes or release of *mMCP-1* in BALB/c mice sensitized to WP (Figure 3),
316 what allows inferring that it is likely not to induce clinical symptoms in patients diagnosed
317 with allergy to cow's milk proteins. This observation is in line with other studies that
318 reported that partially hydrolysed whey-based formulas do not to elicit anaphylactic
319 reactions in C3H/HeOuJ mice (Knipping et al., 2012; van Esch et al., 2010, 2011 a) or
320 Brown Norway rats (Bøgh et al., 2015) sensitized to whey proteins. In fact, the degree of
321 hydrolysis β -Lg, the dominant whey protein causing allergic reactions in mice sensitized
322 to whey, correlates with its allergenic reactivity and the complete removal of intact β -Lg
323 abolishes its ability to activate mast cells and to trigger anaphylaxis *in vivo* (Bossios et
324 al., 2011; López-Expósito et al., 2012).

325 Less is known on the capacity to induce sensitization of hydrolysed versus intact
326 allergens, including β -Lg. Hydrolysis has been reported to reduce the sensitizing potency
327 of cow's milk formulas (Niggemann et al., 2001). However, depending on the hydrolysis
328 conditions, the sensitizing potential of hydrolysed food products can be maintained, or
329 even enhanced, if new epitopes are formed (Krogsho et al., 2014). Thus, Ara h1
330 hydrolysed in low molecular weight products retain IgE-binding and T-stimulatory
331 properties (Eiwegger et al., 2006), and it is able to sensitize Brown Norway rats by the
332 i.p. route, as long as there is the right combination of peptides with an adjuvant effect or
333 the peptides are in an aggregated state (Bøgh et al., 2009, 2012). The hydrolysis products
334 of β -Lg with masses lower than 4.5 kDa fail to induce IgE, IgG1 and IgA antibodies in
335 this rat model, despite they form aggregated complexes (Bøgh et al., 2013), but this may
336 not hold true for bigger fragments.

337 As judged by the antibody responses, HWP exhibited a much less sensitizing capacity
338 than WP. Administration to mice of HWP plus CT did not lead to the production of WP-
339 specific antibodies nor to allergic signs upon WP challenge (Figures 3 and 4), and thus,
340 complies with the European Guidelines which preclude that hypoallergenic hydrolysed
341 formula induce sensitisation, in animals, to the intact proteins from which they are
342 manufactured. Nevertheless, HWP increased the levels of non-specific IgE and IgG1, as
343 compared with the control group, and even if it cannot mount a detectable specific IgE
344 response, it was able to generate a HWP-specific IgG1 response, indicating that the
345 peptides contained in the hydrolysate maintained residual immunogenicity (Figure 4).
346 Furthermore, the PCA assays indicated that the IgG1 antibodies generated were
347 functional, that is, potentially able to trigger local allergic responses (Figure 5). The
348 development of food allergy in mouse models has been described to occur through two
349 independent pathways, comprising either IgE and mast cells or IgG1 and macrophages

350 (Finkelman, 2005). Although, in contrast to systemic anaphylaxis, PCA is entirely mast
351 cell-dependent, in addition to IgE, it can also be mediated by a fraction of IgG1 antibodies
352 (known as anaphylactic IgG1) whose binding to mast cells is promoted by the Th2
353 cytokine IL-4 (Finkelman, 2007). In any case, the low levels of serum HWP-specific IgG1
354 generated, and the fact that very high allergen concentrations are required to induce
355 anaphylaxis by the IgG pathway explain why neither oral nor i.p challenge with HWP
356 induced anaphylaxis in HWP immunized mice (Figure 3). On the other hand, there is no
357 evidence for the clinical relevance of IgG-mediated food allergy in humans (Finkelman
358 et al., 2016)

359 IgG1 from sera of mice sensitized to WP were also reactive towards plate-bound HWP
360 (Figure 4). Despite the resistance of β -Lg to pepsin digestion, it is likely that mice
361 immunized orally to WP and HWP become sensitized to similar fragments, although the
362 higher level of HWP-specific IgG1 found in the HWP group, as compared to the WP
363 group, suggests that HWP could provide more and/or new sensitizing epitopes.

364 Spleen cells from mice sensitized to WP exhibited similar proliferative responses to
365 stimulation with WP and HWP (Table 1). Furthermore, HWP induced a significant
366 production of IL-13 and IL-5 from the splenocytes of WP-sensitized mice, which was
367 comparable to that induced by intact β -Lg (Figure 6 a and c). These results show that
368 HWP contained immunodominant T cell epitopes able to mount Th2 responses. These, in
369 mice, are responsible for the maturation of B cells into plasma cells that produce IgE and
370 IgG1, and for the generation of inflammatory responses that mediate anaphylaxis to a
371 great extent (Oyoshi et al., 2014). Furthermore, the splenocytes of HWP sensitized mice
372 responded to stimulation with HWP with a significantly increased secretion of IL-13 and
373 IL-5, which was similar to that induced by WP. These observations, together with the

374 lack of a clear Th1 (IFN- γ and TNF- α)-stimulating effect (figure 6 b and d) indicate that,
375 regardless of being hypoallergenic, HWP is able to prime mice for allergic reactions,
376 albeit less than WP.

377 Hydrolysates that show a reduced IgE reactivity and maintain T cell-stimulating abilities
378 have proved, in mice, to be a safe treatment for food allergy, working through the same
379 mechanisms as whole protein immunotherapy (Kulis et al., 2012). In addition, partially
380 hydrolysed β -Lg, as well as intact β -Lg, unlike short tryptic peptides, can prevent further
381 sensitization to this allergen (Adel-Patient et al., 2011; 2012); and partial, but not
382 extensively hydrolysed whey, with limited sensitizing properties, retained the putative
383 capacity to prevent allergic symptoms when given orally to mice before sensitization (van
384 Esch et al., 2011 b). The immuno-stimulating potential seems to be mainly supported by
385 the combination of the generated peptides, and particularly by large ones resulting from
386 partial hydrolysis (Pecquet et al., 2000). In this respect, high hydrostatic pressure can
387 produce, in minutes, a hypoallergenic hydrolysate of whey proteins, containing 50% of
388 peptides with molecular masses between 10 and 3 kDa, which retained sufficiently
389 immunogenicity to stimulate Th2 responses, but not enough to generate specific IgE or
390 IgG antibodies that could mediate systemic anaphylaxis. In view of these characteristics,
391 the hydrolysate could be used in the management of milk allergy in diagnosed patients or
392 to induce tolerance to milk whey proteins in therapeutic or preventive approaches.

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395 **Supplementary information**

396 **Supplementary table 1.** Peptide sequences, identified by RP-HPLC-MS/MS (ESI-
397 MS/MS), in the hydrolysate of whey proteins with pepsin obtained at 400MPa during 30
398 minutes (HWP).

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569 **Figure captions**

570 **Figure 1.** RP-HPLC patterns of whey proteins (a), their hydrolysates with pepsin at
571 atmospheric pressure during 4 (b), 8 (c) and 24 hours (d), and under high pressure (400
572 MPa) during 30 min (e).

573 **Figure 2.** Peptide mass distribution in the hydrolysates of whey proteins with pepsin at
574 atmospheric pressure during 24 hours (black bars), and under high pressure (400 MPa)
575 during 30 minutes (white bars). Bars represent the masses included in each range as
576 percentage of all the masses detected by MALDI-TOF (means \pm SEM, n= 3).

577 **Figure 3.** Anaphylaxis in control mice and mice administered whey proteins (WP) or WP
578 hydrolysed with pepsin at 400 MPa during 30 min (HWP) plus cholera toxin,
579 intraperitoneally challenged with WP or HWP. (a) Anaphylactic symptom score, (b) body
580 temperature, and (c) and serum concentration of mouse mast cell protease 1 (*mMCP-1*).
581 Data are expressed as medians (a) or means (b and c) \pm SEM (n= 6). * P< 0.05.

582 **Figure 4.** Total and specific IgE, IgG1 and IgA levels at 7, 14, 21, 28 and 35 (after
583 challenge) days in sera from control mice and mice administered whey proteins (WP) or
584 WP hydrolysed with pepsin at 400 MPa during 30 min (HWP) plus cholera toxin. (a)
585 Total IgE, (b) WP-specific IgE, (c) total IgG1, (d) WP-specific IgG1, (e) total IgA, (f)
586 WP-specific IgA and (g) HWP-specific IgG1. Data are means \pm SEM (n=6). Different
587 lowercase letters (a-c) indicate significant differences (P< 0.05) among days for each
588 mouse group; different uppercase letters (A-D) letters indicate significant differences (P<
589 0.05) among mouse groups at each day.

590 **Figure 5.** Passive cutaneous anaphylaxis assay (PCA) with unheated and heated (56°C
591 for 3 hours) sera from mice administered whey proteins (WP) or WP hydrolysed with
592 pepsin at 400 MPa during 30 min (HWP) plus cholera toxin. Allergen-specific dye
593 extravasation was calculated by correcting the WP or HWP induced absorbance with the

594 absorbance of the supernatant of the ear injected with pooled control sera. Data are means
595 \pm SEM (n= 2). Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (P< 0.05).

596 **Figure 6.** Effects of whey proteins (WP), the major proteins α -lactalbumin (α -La) and β -
597 lactoglobulin (β -Lg), and WP hydrolysed with pepsin at 400 MPa during 30 min (HWP)
598 on the secretion of IL-13 (a), IL-5 (b), IFN- γ (c) and TNF- α (d) by splenocytes from
599 control mice and mice administered WP or HWP plus cholera toxin. Data are means \pm
600 SEM (n=6). Different lowercase letters (a-c) indicate significant differences (P< 0.05)
601 among stimuli for each mouse group; different uppercase letters (A-C) indicate
602 significant differences (P< 0.05) among mouse groups for each stimulus.

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612 **Table 1.** Effects of whey proteins (WP) and WP hydrolysed with pepsin at 400 MPa
613 during 30 min (HWP) on the proliferation, assessed by CFSE labelling, of splenocytes
614 from control mice and mice administered WP or HWP plus cholera toxin. Cells stimulated
615 with 2.5 μ g/mL of concanavalin A (ConA) were used as positive control, and RPMI-
616 treated cells as negative control. Data are means \pm SEM (n= 6).

		Proliferation index
Control	ConA	2.5 ± 0.2 ^{aA}
	RPMI	0.1 ± 0.1 ^{bA}
	WP	0.1 ± 0.1 ^{bB}
	HWP	0.2 ± 0.1 ^{bB}
WP	ConA	2.63 ± 0.3 ^{aA}
	RPMI	0.1 ± 0.0 ^{cA}
	WP	0.6 ± 0.1 ^{bA}
	HWP	0.6 ± 0.1 ^{bA}
HWP	ConA	2.1 ± 0.5 ^{aA}
	RPMI	0.1 ± 0.0 ^{cA}
	WP	0.7 ± 0.1 ^{bA}
	HWP	0.7 ± 0.04 ^{bA}

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618 ^{a-b} Different lowercase letters indicate significant differences (P<0.05) within the columns
619 for each mouse group.

620 ^{A-C} Different uppercase letters indicate significant differences (P<0.05) between the
621 mouse groups for each stimulus.

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